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IMPLEMENTING CONSTRUCTIVIST PEDAGOGY IN ELT CLASSROOM

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Abstract

The article considers Constructivist pedagogy implementation in the Armenian secondary schools. It investigates the results of practicing Constructivist theory in ELT classrooms. We examined how learners form their own representations of the world and receive new information based on their prior background knowledge as they experience and reflect on it. Thus learning becomes engaging and cooperative. The article considers the principles of constructive teaching, as well as it derives the differences between traditional classroom and constructivist classroom. It also introduces interactive implications for the ELT classroom by engaging students with real-life applications of how to use a tool instead of simply giving a list of prescribed instructions.

Keywords: Constructivist pedagogy, Constructivist learning theory, collaborative learning, constructivist teaching methods, principles and strategies of constructivist teaching.

*“Each time one prematurely teaches a child something
he could have discovered himself,
that child is kept from inventing it and
consequently, from understanding it completely.”
Jean Piaget*

Constructivism is a philosophy of learning founded on the premise that, by reflecting on our experiences, we construct our own understanding of the world we live in. Each of us generates our own “rules and mental models”, which we use to make sense of our experiences.

Constructivism as a learning theory/ A brief history

Constructivism as a theory which is defined as a learning process when the learners construct knowledge rather than just passively input the information provided. As people experience the world and reflect upon those experiences, they build their own representations and incorporate new information into

their pre-existing knowledge (schemas). The teacher who implements constructivism at classes they believe that in order to learn, students need as many hands-on experiences with objects, skills, and people as possible. Constructivism provides students with rich experiences and encourages them to draw their own conclusions.

Jean Piaget is considered the founder of the constructivist view of learning. As a biologist, he was interested in how an organism adapts to the environment and how previous mental knowledge contributes to behaviors. Knowledge is not a snapshot of reality; in order to understand something, you don't just simply look at it and make a mental copy of it. In order to truly recognize the environment, we must act on it. According to

Piaget (1964), learning is modeling, transforming, and understanding the way in which something is constructed. Through interactions with the environment, our interpretation of the world changes automatically. Views on separate constructs can be changed in different ways. Instead of there being a stimulus and then a response as a means of learning, Piaget (1964) proposed that there is actually a circular relationship between the two; a stimulus can cause a response, and that response can affect the way in which the next stimulus is viewed. One's cognitive schema, or the way one thinks of a topic or object, is updated by external stimuli. Schemas can be adapted to the stimuli by either assimilation or accommodation. Assimilation takes new information from the environment and fits it with the pre-existing schema, whereas accommodation is the process of changing cognitive schemas in order to accept something new from the environment. Both of these processes can be used simultaneously and alternately throughout life.

Constructivism as a theory can be successful in the teaching and educational process as students learn experientially rather than just from the textbook. Students are encouraged to use their critical thinking, deductive reasoning, and analytical abilities to articulate their thoughts and come up with solutions [4, 23-26].

Students gain knowledge through practical application and their own interpretation of the outcomes. There are numerous conversations and inquiry-based

learning techniques applied to the process. Therefore, learning increasingly focuses on connecting ideas and applying concepts rather than simply ingesting information.

Constructivism in learning theory becomes more centered on the actual application of the principles for the instructors. In contrast to the traditional learning environment, constructivism encourages instructors to take a back seat and let students decide which information is relevant to their learning. The instructors' role evolves into facilitators guiding students on the concepts and encouraging them to ask deeper questions.

The education of the future has to produce students able to work independently or in a team environment. They must be problem solvers and critical thinkers. They must know how to go about learning something new. In order to memorize majority of the obtained information the educators must teach students the skills to acquire new knowledge on their own and use it to come up with novel solutions to problems. This does not mean that content is not important or should not be taught. Students need to learn content from a wide variety of curriculum areas for many reasons. They need to have a shared understanding and background [7, 13-32].

If we compare traditional way of learning/teaching to constructive learning/teaching, we will have the following picture:

Table 2.

Differences of traditional and constructive classrooms

Traditional Classroom	Constructive Classroom
Learners are recipients of knowledge.	The interaction in the class is reciprocal rather than teacher-centered.
Knowledge is seen as inert.	Teaching is flexible, engaging and contextual.
Repetition is dominant.	Learning is based on observation and reflection.
Emphasis is on basic skills.	Emphasis is on encourages interaction and cooperation among students and teachers.
Learners work alone.	Students' voices are heard mostly rather than the teachers'.
Teacher's role is directive, rooted in authority.	Teacher encourages students to higher-level thinking.

If we could change a typical course, where all we do is lecturing, to something more productive (we might as well just hand out our notes), and let the students try something, see how it works, reflect on how to do it differently, then try it again and again, until it works better. The only way a skill is developed—skiing, cooking, writing, thinking critically, or solving thermodynamics problems—is practice.

Learning is essentially a discovery process. We are all natural learners. As babies, we discover things by ourselves before we can be told. Even when we understand enough to be told, we still need to try things

out for ourselves. The understanding cycle - expectation failure - explanation - reminding - generalization - is a natural one. No one teaches it to us. We are not taught to have goals, nor to attempt to develop plans to achieve those goals by adapting old plans from similar situations. We need not be taught this because the process is so basic to what comprises intelligence. Learning is a natural act. Accordingly, we need to transform all training and education so that it looks, feels, and is like doing [12,4-29].

Table 1. Principles of Constructive teaching

The goal of constructivist instructing should be to portray how to do tasks instead of defining how to learn to do the task. According to constructivist theory, micromanagement of students is not an effective means of instilling learning. Effective teaching involves engaging the student with real-world applications of how to use a tool instead of simply giving a list of prescribed instructions. A good constructivist teaching style involves presenting information in a variety of different ways by revising the content at different times and applying it to different purposes and contexts.

Methods that can be encouraged constructivist learning in ELT classroom:

1. Modeling an activity.
2. Actively coaching a student.
3. Collaborative learning with peers in order to share views a. Debates b. Discussions c. Peer reviews.
4. Assignments centered around transferring knowledge and skills from situations addressed in lecture and/or reading to novel or real-world situations.
5. Reflective analysis of a topic.
6. Mental maps and summaries that point out the relation of the parts of a topic to the whole.

While investigating the reality in Armenian educational settings we suggest that the first step that should be taken is for teachers change their attitudes towards students. But what kinds of attitudes need to be changed? Usually, some language teachers look upon their students as empty vessels, which require to be filled with information. In fact, these teachers disregard their students' qualities and ideas. In addition, they do not allow their students to come into their own and express themselves. In the case of passive learners, teacher is the only one who speaks. Such teachers expect their students to do as they are told and they do not allow them to ask "why" or "how". This kind of attitudes will destroy the opportunities for learning and critical thinking. The solution to this problem is that teachers should become patient listeners to learners'

opinions and questions. Teachers should do their best to avoid these attitudes and move to being open-minded in their attitudes and actions. In the following section some of the strategies which can help teachers reinforce critical thinking of their students are presented.

When the teacher answers questions or asks them, some challenging questions such as "Why is it so? What do you think about...? What is your idea about...?" etc. can help students think critically. These are mostly influential in verbal exchanges in the language class. R Ennis (1992) proposes the three underlying strategies as "Reflection, Reason, and Alternatives."

1. Encourage your students to be Reflective, to wait and think, instead of making impulsive judgments, or accepting the first thought that occurs in their mind, or promptly accepting whatever is manifested in the media. Many students accept whatever they are told especially if something is said by someone who they trust e.g. their friends or if something is written in books and newspapers. As such, students should be taught to wait after receiving ideas and think deeply and then accept them in case the information corresponds to logic and reasoning. This will lead to improvement in their critical thinking ability.

2. Kindly ask questions such as "How do you know", "what are the Reasons?" so as to make sure they have underlying reasons for their ideas and to search for rationales for others' views.

3. Highlight alertness for alternatives, hypotheses, conclusions, explanations, points of views etc. Students should understand that there is no fixed idea and most of the times, there are some alternatives if the point be viewed from a different angle. This point can be taught to students and they should be sharp enough to devise new options. You can ask them e.g. "Is it possible to solve this problem in another way?" or "Do you know any cheaper way for dealing with these costs?"

4. Give your students adequate time to ponder

about questions and situations. This is vital for deep thinking and logical reasoning.

5. In a debate, write down each student's statement on the board with the student's name, so that the student receives attention and assumes some responsibility, and invite other students to comment on it. This will also lead to improvement in students' self-esteem which consequently gives them impetus for thinking critically.

6. Ask students to formulate their own questions. They need to realize that it is not just the teacher who can ask questions, students also have the right to ask. The students' understanding of the roles which they have in the process of teaching/learning is one of the first steps in leading them toward critical thinking.

As it is widely known the lecture format of learning is a venerable and popular approach to content delivery in higher education; however, it frequently does not encourage active learning or critical thinking on the part of students. Those new to the teaching profession often adopt the lecture format because it is both teacher-centered and comes with a strong academic tradition. Unfortunately, it is very difficult to increase a student's critical thinking skills with the lecture format. Topics are discussed sequentially rather than critically, and students tend to memorize the material since the lecture method facilitates the delivery of large amounts of information. The student is placed in a passive rather than an active role since the teacher does the talking, the questioning, and, thus, most of the thinking Maiorana [9, 53-64].

Active learning can make the course more enjoyable for both teachers and students, and, most importantly, it can cause students to think critically. For this to happen, educators must give up the belief that students cannot learn the subject at hand unless the teacher covers it. While it is useful for students to gain some exposure to the material through pre-class readings and overview lectures, students really do not understand it until they actively do something with it and reflect on the meaning of what they are doing.

To conclude, we can state that Constructivist teaching gives students ownership of learning, and it focuses on transferable skills. Students learn questioning, they gain communication and social skills. By im-

plementing Constructive pedagogy instructors encourage students to construct their own knowledge through experiences and activities versus being lectured on abstract concepts. Educators who teach using a constructivist pedagogy promote skills and subject mastery through hands-on lessons and self-guided learning.

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